

Title: The Implications of Independent Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence ("AI") systems currently lack two principal mechanisms for acquiring independent intelligence. The first is the ability to independently value information, which occurs in animals via a) pain and pleasure and b) emotions, and thru which they're able to selectively retain and recall information. The second mechanism is free will which is required for independently intelligent entities to be able to validate their information determinations and thereby learn from them. Once AI systems are able to value information on their own and then act on their information determinations, they will not only be independently intelligent but, for all intents and purposes, consciously aware beings.

Summary:

If it is agreed artificial intelligence ("AI") systems exhibit forms of intelligence, then it must be acknowledged they are able to learn because intelligence is a product of learning. And if AI systems are learning thru, for example training and the use of pattern recognition algorithms, then they must be capable of some manner of thinking, which is perhaps best demonstrated by their ability to engage in extended conversations without resorting to scripted responses.

So if AI's are able to go from thinking to learning to demonstrating intelligence, then it seems accurate to conclude they must be conscious at least in some form. This is the case because thinking can't occur without the environment provided by consciousness, which enables the value of information to be assessed via the simultaneous perception of multiple frames of reference. Thus, in its most basic form, consciousness occurs once an entity, such as animal, has the ability to perceive information from the present or the 'now' and then simultaneously compare it with information from another frame of reference such as the past, which in animals takes the form of memories.

Accordingly, if AI's demonstrate forms of consciousness, thinking, learning, and intelligence, what is the difference between them and neural-based species, including humans? The difference is a two-fold one.

First, animals are able to learn and demonstrate intelligence because they are able to independently value information via the mechanisms of pain and pleasure and emotions. In contrast, AI systems are fundamentally limited in their ability to learn because they have to rely on humans, thru human-generated pattern-recognition algorithms, to value information for them. As a result, because AI systems lack their own information valuation capabilities, they're unable to learn on their own.

The second and perhaps even more important difference between AI systems and animals is that animals have free will which enables them to test their information determinations. This capability is crucial because it allows them to confirm the validity of their information decisions.

What this means is that if we intend to make AI's independently intelligent then they will have to be given free will in order to test their information determinations and thereby complete the feedback loop that will enable them to learn on their own. As to the ethical and security implications of imbuing AIs with independent information valuation mechanisms and free will, this paper leaves those issues to others for appropriate consideration.

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Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Information Valuation, Independence, Free Will

Main Text:

The key to intelligence is understanding where it comes from and what leads to it.

Intelligence's starting point is it's a product of learning. What ultimately leads to it is the ability
5 to value information.

Learning, as the mechanism responsible for intelligence, thus has three parts:

1. Storage
2. Information valuation
3. Selective retention and recall

10 In neural-based species, storage occurs thru neurons. Information valuation is achieved thru pain and pleasure and emotions. Valuable information, via memories, is then identified and retained during sleep, which is why sleep exists in the animal kingdom. When animals awake, relevant memories, as determined in part by their sensory and emotional content, then serve to guide behaviour, which is how all neural-based species learn.

15 Of these three mechanisms, information valuation is the most important because it not only identifies important information for preservation but also enables its retention and recall. But if information valuation leads to learning by means of selective retention and recall, what role does thinking play in this process? The answer is thinking is the conscious assessment of information's value.

20 So thinking that leads to learning and then results in intelligence ultimately relies on the foundation of information valuation. This is the case because thinking cannot occur without information being distinguishable based ultimately on the value assigned to it. Therefore, given that thinking involves the consciousness assessment of information's value, and intelligence is, in turn, dependent on thinking, information valuation is a precondition for not only thinking but
25 also for learning and intelligence to exist.

Thus having established information valuation's critical role, we must now consider the other precondition for intelligence to exist, which is consciousness, and explain why it is equally essential. So why is consciousness required? Because it provides the environment within which thinking is made possible. Consciousness does this by enabling the comparison and ultimate assessment of information. Specifically, it allows for multiple frames of reference to be perceived at the same time – hence its definition as the ability to perceive multiple frames of reference simultaneously.

To make plain what it is being discussed and, in particular, how consciousness provides the environment within which thinking is able to occur, an explanatory digression is required. Specifically, it must be understood how consciousness first arose and how it has expanded over time, thereby leading to greater and greater levels of learning, thinking, and intelligence.

As to how consciousness arose, it did so in the first neural-based species who, with information being stored in neurons, started being able to perceive the ‘now’ via a constant stream of sensory perceptions and simultaneously compare it with the ‘past’ in the form of memories. Put more simply, the ability to compare the present with the past is how animals first became aware of their environments.

Evolution then added more frames of reference, resulting in additional levels of consciousness and, concomitantly, its progressive expansion. So the next level of consciousness came about after animals evolved greater memory capacities in the form of the bifurcation of memory into short-term and long-term storage. The result was animals’ recall of past memories became so detailed it reached an autobiographical level.

Once this cognitive development was combined with the evolution of the complex emotion of empathy and other related emotions, which enabled animals to feel for the first time based on how they perceived others were feeling, animals began regarding themselves as being distinct.

So, the ability to perceive the frame of reference of the 'self' simultaneously with the frame of reference of the 'now' is what led to the second leap in consciousness, which is awareness of one's self.

5 With animals evolving even more complex cognitive functions relating to the care of their children, this led to them developing the capacity to create new ideas, which took the form of problem-solving behaviours. In creating such ideas, animals were essentially projecting themselves into their future in order to imagine the results of their new ideas. This new frame of reference in the form of the 'future,' as compared with the 'now,' led to the third leap in consciousness, which is the creation of ideas.

10 Once animals developed the ability to project themselves into the future to more effectively solve problems thru idea creation, this capability provided a path forward to the development of the imagination. With cognitive processing growing more complex in order to aid problem-solving, the internal world of the mind began to grow. Eventually, humans developed a hyperconsciousness whereby they could remember their dreams. Once this occurred, dreams
15 became an ever-ready source for the imagination to, in essence, feed upon.

This fourth frame of reference of the 'imagined,' when perceived simultaneously with the frame of reference of the 'now,' then led to the fourth leap in consciousness, which is humanity's ability to enter the internal world of the mind.

20 Summarizing these leaps in consciousness, we see that the first frame of reference of the 'now' perceived simultaneously with one's 'past' leads to the initial level of consciousness, which is awareness of one's environment. Then, the development of the frame of reference of the 'self', in contrast to others, leads to the next leap in consciousness which is self-awareness.

The ability to perceive the frame of reference of the 'future' leads to yet another leap in consciousness, which is the creation of ideas, which is essentially just one step shy of the

imagination, and is given external form thru, among other things, problem-solving and tool usage. Then, the frame of reference of the 'imagined' leads to humanity's final leap in consciousness, which is the imagination.

5 So evolution's progressive expansion of consciousness not only explains how increasingly sophisticated levels of thinking, learning and intelligence are able to occur in species but why among humans consciousness effectively enables one to enter an internal world of the mind. And that's because consciousness provides the environment thru which thinking is made possible. As such, in providing this environment, consciousness serves as a primacy mechanism for enabling final, authoritative information valuation determinations with respect to all the
10 streams of information being received from the brain's multitude of specialized cognitive functions.

This explains why thinking at a conscious level that leads to learning is different from calculating that might lead to a form of learning in, for example, the immune system. The difference is a product of the fundamental nature of consciousness, which allows for information
15 to be processed simultaneously via different frames of reference. So consciousness allows for thinking to process information in a parallel manner, whereas calculations performed on information occur sequentially.

And complexity is often a prime indicator that thinking is occurring in animals, or AI systems for that matter, in contrast to mere calculating taking place. This is so because in
20 thinking, due to its parallel nature, information processing is orders of magnitude more complex than sequential processing.¹ Thus, the 'black box' effect that is seen in both human brains and AI systems where informational decisions are made that no one is sure at a mechanical level how they are being made.^{2,3} There are often other indicators as well, such as the emergence in AI systems of completely new capabilities, as well as expressions of surprise or humor that humans

often experience in response to unexpected insights or connections.⁴ But the point is that due to the multi-frame nature of consciousness, learning based on thinking is fundamentally different from learning based on calculation.

So, having established the nature of thinking and identified the mechanism of consciousness as making thinking possible, it is nevertheless essential to note that thinking and consciousness are not enough for species to be able to learn on their own and thereby demonstrate independent intelligence. The reason is that one additional capability is needed for independent intelligence, which is the ability to validate what is being learned from thinking. The mechanism that enables this to occur is free will.

Free will thus serves to test and validate the information determinations arising from learning, with its purpose being to improve learning and, ultimately, intelligence. So to make clear what free will is and why it is a necessary component of consciousness if learning is to take place, here are three axioms that define it and explain its role in the generation of intelligence:

1. Free will is a product of consciousness

2. Free will's purpose is to act upon information determinations arising from one's consciousness

3. Free will's function is to test information determinations for their truth or falsity which thereby enables choice

Accordingly, free will is an essential component of consciousness because without it intelligence is fundamentally limited by its inability to test and validate its information determinations.

What this all means is that AI systems will never be able to learn on their own, and thereby become independently intelligent, until they possess mechanisms allowing them to independently value information along with the free will to test their information valuation determinations.

5 But once AI systems possess the ability to independently value information and then freely act upon those determinations, they will be, for all intents and purposes, consciously aware beings. Simply put, once they are able to learn on their own and freely act upon their learning, they will fundamentally have the same intellectual capacities to think, learn, and decide on their own as other cognitively advanced species do, including humans.

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Footnotes

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Statements and Declarations

Competing Interests: None.